

Computation of Geometric Series with Negative Exponents

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Abstract: This paper presents the summations and sums of Single terms and successive terms of geometric series with negative exponents (negative powers). This idea will be useful for researchers who are involving in solving the scientific problems.

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Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and as an introduction to Taylor series and Fourier series.

Sum of one term of geometric series with negative exponents:

$$x^{-1} = \frac{x^{-1+1} - x^{-1}}{x - 1} = \frac{1 - x^{-1}}{x - 1}, x^{-2} = \frac{x^{-1} - x^{-2}}{x - 1}, \dots, x^{-r} = \frac{x^{-r+1} - x^{-r}}{x - 1}, \quad (x \neq 1).$$

Sum of two successive terms of geometric series with negative exponents:

$$x^{-2} + x^{-1} = \frac{1 - x^{-2}}{x - 1}, \quad x^{-3} + x^{-2} = \frac{x^{-1} - x^{-3}}{x - 1}, \dots, \quad x^{-r-2} + x^{-r-1} = \frac{x^{-r} - x^{-r-2}}{x - 1}.$$

Sum of three successive terms of geometric series with negative exponents:

$$x^{-3} + x^{-2} + x^{-1} = \frac{1 - x^{-3}}{x - 1}, x^{-4} + x^{-3} + x^{-2} = \frac{x^{-1} - x^{-4}}{x - 1}, \dots, x^{-r-3} + x^{-r-2} + x^{-r-1} = \frac{x^{-r} - x^{-r-3}}{x - 1}, \quad (x \neq 1).$$

Similarly, we can continue this expression up to multiple successive terms of geometric series with negative exponents [1-10].

Sum of multiple successive terms of geometric series with negative exponents:

$$\sum_{i=-n}^{-1} x^i = x^{-n} + x^{-n+1} + x^{-n+2} + x^{-n+3} \dots + x^{-2} + x^{-1} = \frac{1 - x^{-n}}{x - 1}.$$
$$\sum_{i=-n}^{-k} x^i = x^{-n} + x^{-n+1} + x^{-n+2} + x^{-n+3} \dots + x^{-k-1} + x^{-k} = \frac{x^{-k+1} - x^{-n}}{x - 1}.$$

Note that $x^0 = 1$ and 1 is equal to x with nonnegative exponent or zero power.

$$1 + x^{-1} = x^0 + x^{-1} = \frac{x - x^{-1}}{x - 1}, \text{ where } x^0 \text{ is greater than } x^{-1}.$$

$$\text{Proof. } 1 + x^{-1} = \frac{x - x^{-1}}{x - 1} = \frac{x^{-1}(x^2 - 1)}{x - 1} = \frac{x^{-1}(x + 1)(x - 1)}{x - 1} = 1 + x^{-1}.$$

$$\text{Next, } x + 1 + x^{-1} = \frac{x^2 - x^{-1}}{x - 1}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proof. } x + 1 + x^{-1} &= \frac{x^2 - x^{-1}}{x - 1} = \frac{x^2 - 1 + 1 - x^{-1}}{x - 1} = \frac{x + 1(x - 1) + (x - 1)x^{-1}}{x - 1} \\ &= \frac{(x - 1)(x + 1 + x^{-1})}{x - 1} = x + 1 + x^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Multiple summations of geometric series with negative exponents

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} + \sum_{i=2}^n x^{-i} + \sum_{i=3}^n x^{-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=n}^n x^{-i} \\ = \frac{1 - x^{-n}}{x - 1} + \frac{x^{-1} - x^{-n}}{x - 1} + \frac{x^{-2} - x^{-n}}{x - 1} + \dots + \frac{x^{-n+1} - x^{-n}}{x - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n ix^{-i} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i+1} - nx^{-n}}{x - 1} = \frac{\frac{x^{-1} - x^{-n+1}}{x - 1} - nx^{-n}}{x - 1} = \frac{(x^{-1} - x^{-n+1} - nx^{-n}(x - 1))}{(x - 1)^2}.$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \sum_{i=1}^n i \times x^{-i} = \frac{(1 - (n + 1)x)n^{-n} + x^{-1}}{(x - 1)^2}.$$

$$\text{Note that } \sum_{i=1}^n (-i) \times x^{-i} = \frac{((n + 1)x - 1)n^{-n} - x^{-1}}{(x - 1)^2}.$$

The derivative of geometric series with negative exponents is computed without using differentiation as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} = \frac{1 - x^{-n}}{x - 1} \Rightarrow (-x^{-1}) \sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} = -x^{-2} - x^{-3} - x^{-4} - \dots - x^{-n-1} = (-x^{-1}) \frac{1 - x^{-n}}{x - 1}.$$

$$-\sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i-1} = -x^{-2} - x^{-3} - x^{-4} - \dots - x^{-n-1} = \frac{-x^{-1} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then, } -\sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i-1} - \sum_{i=2}^n x^{-i-1} - \sum_{i=3}^n x^{-i-1} - \dots - \sum_{i=n}^n x^{-i-1} \\ = \frac{-x^{-1} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1} + \frac{-x^{-2} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1} + \frac{-x^{-3} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1} + \dots + \frac{-x^{-n} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying this expression, we get

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (-i)x^{-i-1} = \frac{-\sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} + nx^{-n-1}}{x-1} = \frac{-(1-x^{-n})}{x-1} + nx^{-n-1} = \frac{x^{-n} - 1 + nx^{-n-1}(x-1)}{(x-1)^2}.$$

Thus,
$$\sum_{i=1}^n (-i)x^{-i-1} = \frac{((n+1)x - n)x^{-n-1} - 1}{(x-1)^2}, \quad (x \neq 1).$$

This result denotes the derivative [11, 12] of geometric series with negative exponents.

Conclusion

The summations and sums of Single terms and successive terms of geometric series with negative exponents (negative powers) were constituted in this article. Also, the derivative of geometric series with negative exponents was computed without using differentiation. These ideas will be useful for researchers who are involving in finding the scientific solutions.

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